

COMPARING MATERIALS USED TO REPAIR DENTAL DECAY: IMPACT ON THE ENVIRONMENT

USE OF AMALGAM IN DENTAL RESTORATIONS

From 2034, the UK and Europe will stop using dental amalgam (a metal filling material) to repair cavities (tooth decay). Dentists may still use amalgam in special cases if it is best for the patient. However, other filling materials, such as glass ionomer and resin composites, may be used more often.

This change follows a gradual move away from using amalgam in the UK and other countries. Some people have concerns about how amalgam affects the environment, especially because it contains mercury. Dental practices use special filters called amalgam separators to reduce mercury entering wastewater. We know less about the environmental impact of other filling materials.

SUPPORTING RESEARCH

Before deciding to stop using amalgam, the Department of Health and Social Care asked the Exeter Policy Research Programme Evidence Review Facility to carry out an independent review. The review looked at the environmental impact of amalgam compared with other filling materials.*

KEY FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- There is not enough research yet to know which filling materials are least harmful to the environment.
- Future research should compare the environmental impact of substances linked with these materials. For example, mercury in amalgam and monomers (chemicals) in other materials.
- Researchers also need to study the carbon emissions linked with filling materials.

Properties of different materials used to repair dental decay

Key definitions

DENTAL AMALGAM: Made from mercury mixed with metals such as silver, tin, and copper.

RESIN BASED COMPOSITE: Tooth-coloured and made from plastic resin and tiny glass or ceramic particles.

GLASS IONOMER: Tooth-coloured and made from glass powder. It bonds to the tooth and releases fluoride to help stop decay.

WHAT IS A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW?

A systematic review brings together studies on the same topic to answer a question. It checks whether the studies show similar results. It also looks at how well the studies were carried out to see how much we can trust the findings

*This review also looked at how different filling materials may affect human health. Please see the separate patient information leaflet for further details.

FURTHER DETAIL: TYPE OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS MEASURED

Dental amalgam		Composite resin
Mercury in waste water (5 studies)		Chemicals in waste water (2 studies)
Mercury in solid waste (3 studies)		X
Mercury in gases released into air (3 studies)		Chemicals in gases released into air (1 study)
Mercury in vapour (3 studies)		X
Mercury in tiny particles in the air (2 studies)		Chemicals in tiny particles in the air (1 study)

- 21 studies looked at how different dental materials affected the environment.
- Only 5 studies compared the environmental impact of one filling material with another. The others looked at only one material.
- Fewer than half measured real environmental impacts such as harm to animals or carbon footprint. The rest only measured possible impacts, such as levels of harmful chemicals in water.
- Most studies looked at mercury from amalgam in water, air or waste. Far fewer studies examined chemicals from other filling materials.

The studies were very different from each other in:

- What they were trying to find out.
- How they did the research (methods).
- Where the research was done.
- Which environmental effects they looked at.

Because of this, it was hard to compare the studies, even when they looked at the same environmental impact.

This made it difficult to compare how different materials affect the environment

Environmental impacts linked to multiple restoration materials: Carbon footprint (1 study) and Animal toxicity (2 studies)

One laboratory study found amalgam was more harmful to animals than other materials. However, it was not clear if the clinic used amalgam separators.

Another study looked at dental clinics which used amalgam separators. It found resin-based composites and glass ionomer cement produced more solid waste than amalgam.

The carbon footprint was lower for GIC than for RBC or amalgam. However, this may be because GIC is used less often.

Overall, current research does not provide clear evidence about which filling materials have the lowest environmental impact. Further research is needed to guide future policy and clinical practice.

Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility

We are one of two research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute of Health and Care Research Policy Research Programme to conduct syntheses of evidence to inform policy development and evaluation across the full policy remit of the DHSC. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the DHSC.

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